

IPHA Student Section Newsletter Spring 2021

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The Illinois Public Health Association (IPHA) Student Section

The goal of this section is to further the development of students, the next generation of professionals in public health and health related disciplines. This section represents and serves student of public health and other health- related disciplines by connecting individuals who are interested in working together on public health and student- related issues.

Contributors

- Seunghyo Wee- editor, University of Illinois Chicago
- Waheed Ogunwale- contributor, University of Illinois Springfield
- Chandani Kothari- contributor, Northern Illinois University
- Asra Mohamadi- contributor, Benedictine University
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Welcome From the IPHA Student Section Chair

Beth Squires, MPH, MCHES, Northern Illinois University

Here's the latest newsletter from the IPHA Student Section! I hope everyone had a successful 2020 – 2021 academic year.

In this newsletter, you will find information on the COVID-19 vaccine to share with your vaccine-hesitant family, friends and colleagues. We all need to work together in our local communities to achieve herd immunity nationwide!

You will also find internship and volunteer opportunities in this newsletter. The summer is a good time to volunteer in your community to gain experience in the field. The students have researched volunteer opportunities around the state to help you in your search. Add to your resume and build onto your professional network by volunteering at a local organization!

Please be on the lookout for upcoming opportunities to serve in the IPHA Student Section. We hope to have another great academic year in 2021 – 2022!

Meet the IPHA Staff

- **Name:** Lanie Kepler
- **Credentials:** MPA
- **Job title and duties?** Executive Assistant; I manage the IPHA Executive Council and IPHA Sections, assist with legislative activities, and help plan IPHA's annual conference.
- **Why did you want to work with IPHA?** I made a connection with IPHA as a graduate intern for the serve Illinois Commission. When I was looking for a new work home, I didn't have to look too far.
- **What are your goals within the organization?** My goal is always to make IPHA successful, so I am happy to fit into whatever role makes that possible.
- **Are there volunteer or internship experiences you would recommend to current students to help them narrow down their interests?** All experience is good experience. Take the internship or volunteer position even if the takeaway is that you figure out what you DON'T want to do. (You should also apply to be an IPHA AmeriCorps members ☺)

- **What part of public health do you find most rewarding?** I enjoy getting to know public health professionals from across the state. The people we work with at IPHA are passionate about what they do and that makes working for them enjoyable.
- **Is there anything you wish someone would have told you as a student working in the public health field?** Public Health needs all specialties- lawyers, administrators, IT, PR, etc. You don't have to be an expert in food safety or vector borne diseases to make an impact.
- **Any advice for students wishing to pursue leadership positions in public health organizations or agencies in their future careers?** Start making connections now. Networking is half the battle.

Public Health Hot Topic: COVID-19 Prevention

Waheed Ogunwale, University of Illinois at Springfield

COVID-19, an emerging disease, caused by a highly contagious virus, SARS-CoV-2, has resulted in global health and economic burden (Bauchner and Fontanarosa, 2020) hence the need for measures to halt or mitigate the spread.

The COVID -19 Treatment Guideline Panel has recommended against the use of any drugs for SARS-CoV-2 pre-exposure prophylaxis except in clinical trials as there is no evidence-based medication known to prevent COVID-19 at the moment (NIH, 2021).

The recommended preventive measures have been designed to halt the transmission of the virus; these include frequent hand washing, maintaining social distance, nose & mouth covering, use of alcohol-based sanitizers, quarantine, vaccination, etc. Girum, Lentiro, & Shewamare, 2020 concluded that that quarantine, contact tracing, and isolation are effective measures of COVID-19 prevention, particularly when integrated.

Bauchner and Fontanarosa, 2020 emphasized effective public health measures (vaccination and others) against treatment interventions. They indicated that the attributable risk for the best interventions towards reducing mortality with COVID-19 disease is 5-10%. Invariably, to prevent death in an individual infected with COVID-19, 10-20 people needed to be treated. These further buttresses the need for preventive measures.

Everyone needs to abide by the CDC guidelines for COVID-19 prevention while mass vaccination continues. The CDC has developed guidelines for both fully vaccinated people and otherwise. Unvaccinated people need to continually wear a mask that covers both the nose and mouth and secures under the chin; this helps protect the individual and others. They also need to stay six feet apart from others outside the home while they avoid close contact with sick people inside the home. Besides, they need to wash their hands often with soap and water and use hand sanitizer if soap and water are not available (CDCa, 2021).

An important preventive measure is a vaccination. Unvaccinated people should get vaccinated as soon as possible as the vaccine is now available to every adult within the US. Vaccination helps protect from COVID-19 and allows the resumption of some pre-pandemic activities excepted where otherwise stated by federal, states, local, tribal, or territorial laws, rules, and regulations including local businesses and workplace guidance (CDCb, 2021). There is the need for individuals to periodically check up on the CDC guidance for updates.

Public Health Information:

Debunking COVID-19 Vaccine Myths

The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has approved four different COVID-19 vaccines for use within the US at present. The hesitancy of vaccination still exists among the population due to some misinformation about the vaccine. In a study conducted by Khubchandani et al, 2021, it was discovered 22% of the research participants were hesitant to take these vaccines when available, hence the need to debunk the myths about the COVID-19 vaccine.

Testing positive for COVID-19 after vaccination: None of the vaccines approved by the FDA at the moment causes a vaccinated individual to test positive for the viral test. A positive antibody test could occur following a previous infection or some level of protection against the virus following vaccination (CDC, 2021).

Vaccination is not needed for previously infected people: There is natural immunity from previous COVID-19 infection. However, early evidence short-term immunity. Some scientists believe in more protection with vaccination; more studies are needed to better explain this (John Hopkins Medicine, 2021).

The vaccine development was rushed and therefore unsafe: The vaccine development was the product of an already existing knowledge. The development was financially supported by governments and philanthropists. There was a need for early development to halt the pandemic (John Hopkins Medicine, 2021).

COVID-19 vaccine may affect fertility and unsafe during pregnancy: There is no evidence at the moment to suggest the COVID-19 vaccine affects fertility or pregnancy in any way. Hence, women with plans to become pregnant in the future can be vaccinated (CDC, 2021).

COVID-19 vaccine side effects are dangerous: COVID-19 vaccination can come with some side effects but are short-term and not dangerous. Some vaccinated individuals reported body aches, headache, fever, injection site pain lasting one to two days; these are all indications of immune system stimulation. Individuals may however be allergic to the vaccine; allergic individuals are however encouraged to discuss with their doctors before vaccination while they carry about their EpiPens (John Hopkins Medicine, 2021).

Summer Physical Activity Advice

Chandani Kothari, Northern Illinois University

The importance of getting regular exercise is probably nothing new to you. The health benefits are well known and established: Regular physical activity can produce long-term health benefits by reducing your risk of many chronic diseases and it can also increase your chances of living longer, help you control your weight, and even help you sleep better. As a busy college student, you may be thinking, *I know this, but I don't have time! I have classes and work and a full life!* Between balancing school responsibilities and maintaining a personal life, exercise and nutrition can easily slip to the bottom of the priority list for college students. Getting into an effective exercise routine now will not only make it easier to build healthy habits that you can take with you into your life after college, but it can actually help you be a more successful student, too.

In conjunction to a healthy diet and an adequate amount of sleep each night, regular exercise contributes to a well-rounded lifestyle. The [Department of Health and Human Services](#) recommends 2.5 to 5 hours of moderate-intensity aerobic exercise or 1.15 to 2.5 hours of high-intensity aerobic activity each week. They also recommend 2 or more days of muscle-strengthening exercises. So, how do you fit this into your week? Here are some tips that may help:

- Exercise before you do anything else. Setting aside some time in the morning to exercise will brighten your mood and keep you energized throughout the day.
- Join a team sport to stay motivated, because you will want to be there for your team. Exercising with a friend, whether it's running, weight-lifting or taking a walk, makes it more enjoyable.
- Try fitness apps and videos. Break the routine by incorporating new exercises.
- Many schools provide fitness facilities on campus for students they can take advantage of for free. Try to squeeze in a workout between classes or head to the gym in the morning.
- Walk or bike to school or try standing at your desk during online classes.

Exercise doesn't have to be something you dread. It can be a time to de-stress and rejuvenate. You just have to find the exercise that works best for you. The options are endless, and the mental and physical results are worth it.

Internship Opportunities & Volunteer Opportunities

<Health Related Internship Opportunities>

The following websites could be used as a guide to help you find a public health internship, but these potential opportunities represent only a fraction of the available positions.

- Abbott Laboratories: <https://www.abbott.com/careers/students/internships.html>
- Advocate Healthcare: <https://jobs.advocatehealth.com/search/>
- Amita Health: <https://www.amitahealth.org/careers/>
- American Dental Association: <https://www.ada.org/en/education-careers>
- American Red Cross: <https://www.redcross.org/local/illinois/chicago-and-northern-illinois/volunteer/internships.html>
- American Society for Microbiology: <https://www.asm.org/Work-at-asm>
- AmeriCorps: www.nationalservice.gov/programs/ Americorps
- Association of Schools & Programs of Public Health: <https://www.aspph.org/study/fellowships-and-internships/aspph-headquarters-internship-program/>
- Boone County IL : <http://www.boonecountyil.org/content/internship-opportunities>
- Doctors Without Borders: <https://www.doctorswithoutborders.org/careers/work-us-office/office-internships>
- Compassionate Care Network (CCN): <https://ccnamerica.com/>

- Clean Cities Coalition Network:
<http://www1.eere.energy.gov/cleancities/amcalpin@anl.gov>
- Edward-Elmhurst Health: <https://www.eehealth.org/careers/>
- EverThrive Illinois: www.everthriveil.org resume@everthriveil.org
- FEMA: <https://www.fema.gov/careers/job-openings>
- Indo-American Center : <https://indoamerican.org/>
- Kendall County Public Health: <http://www.kendallhealth.org/>
- Lake County Public Health: <https://www.lakecountyil.gov/148/Health-Department-Community-Health-Cente>
- Loyola Medicine: <https://www.loyolamedicine.org/jobs>
- McHenry County Public Health: <https://www.mchenrycountyil.gov/county-government/departments-a-i/health-department>
- Northshore Medicine: <https://www.northshore.org/careers/>
- Northwestern Medicine: <https://nmhc.referrals.selectminds.com/>
- Robert Crown Center for Health
Education: <https://www.robertcrown.org/about/careers/>
- Rush Health: <https://www.rush.edu/health-care-professionals/career-opportunities>
- Saheli Study: sahelistudy@northwestern.edu
- Walgreens: <https://jobs.walgreens.com/internships>
- Will County Public Health: <https://willcountyhealth.org/chc/>

<Health Related Volunteer Opportunities in Chicago Area>

Chicago Greater Food Depository

Greater Chicago Food Depository distributes an average of 200,000 pounds of food to those in need across Chicagoland. The food is distributed through partner agencies and programs to reach children, older adults, and veterans.

<https://www.chicagosfoodbank.org/volunteer/>

Chicago Red Cross

The American Red Cross in Chicago and Northern Illinois mobilizes communities and volunteers to prevent, prepare for, and respond to natural and human-caused disasters by delivering health and safety training across the region and 24/7 global emergency communication services. The Red Cross is also the largest supplier of blood products in the country. If you have questions about volunteering, do not hesitate to contact to volunteer service office at 312-729-6222 or volunteerillinois@redcross.org.

<https://www.redcross.org/local/illinois/volunteer.html>

Community health clinic

Please contact Ava Zeligson, Manager of volunteer services, email is preferred. azeligson@communityhealth.org / 773.969.5923

Core Center For HIV and AIDS

2020 W. Harrison; Chicago, IL 60612; 312.572.4500 / Volunteers: Please call the number listed above.

Howard Brown Health

Contact: volunteer@howardbrown.org / Address: 4025 N. Sheridan Road, Chicago, IL 60613

- **Fundraising Events**

Support our three major fundraising events in the Spring and Fall of each year through check-in, coat check, raffle tables, and more.

- Broadway Youth Center
Lend your support at Broadway Youth Center (BYC) Drop-In, where we provide youth-centered support to LGBTQ youth, youth experiencing homelessness, and/or street-based youth by providing basic needs and linkage to resources and services.
- Reception Specialist
Support the Administrative offices of Howard Brown. Requires receptionist or administrative experience. Shifts are available from 9 a.m. to 5 p.m. Monday through Friday.
- Safer Sex Kit Assembly
Put together packages of personal hygiene items and safer sex items that will be distributed at our clinics and in the community.

Infant Welfare Society of Chicago

3600 W. Fullerton Ave.; Chicago, IL 60647; 773.782-2800; www.infantwelfare.org

Volunteers: Please call Ana Quinones at the number listed above.

Lakeview Pantry; food for today, hope for tomorrow

One of Chicago's largest and longest-operating food pantries, Lake view Pantry's mission is to eliminate hunger and poverty in our community by providing food to fill the basic need of hungry people; empowering our clients to gain independence through innovative social service programs; and raising awareness of hunger and poverty and working towards solutions to eliminate them. The first step of becoming a Lakeview Pantry Volunteer is to complete registration. (You can find the link blow attached link.) For more information about this program, do not hesitate to contact them to volunteers@lakeviewpantry.org or 773-525-1777.

<https://www.lakeviewpantry.org/volunteer/>
<https://www.lakeviewpantry.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Volunteer-Orientation-Welcome-Packet-2021.pdf>

Pacific Garden Missions

1458 S. Canal St.; Chicago, IL 60607; 312.281.4801 • www.pgm.org / Volunteers: Please call the number listed above.

Refugee One

RefugeeOne serves refugee populations around the world who resettle in Chicago through the U.S State Department Refugee Admissions Program. RefugeeOne provides resettlement services, English language training, workforce development, Trauma-informed mental health care, vocational sewing, youth & young adult programming, women's services, and immigration assistance.

<http://www.refugeeone.org/volunteer.html>

UI Health

We are a diverse and dynamic group of over 600 volunteers dedicated to providing exceptional care and services to patients and families. The program builds meaningful connections, caring relationships, and positive engagement between volunteers, patients, and families, and promotes the importance of a positive and engaged patient experience. In order to ensure the most rewarding volunteer experience, we ask that our volunteers make a commitment of 12 months of service with a minimum of 8 hours each month. Volunteers must be 16 years of age or older and complete a drug screening, health assessment, and criminal background check. Our opportunities are non-clinical, do not consist of any clinical experiences, and are not related to any accreditation processes for student programs. If you have any questions about our program or requirements, do not hesitate to contact the volunteer service office at 312.355.4325 or volserv@uic.edu. You can follow UI Health Volunteer services on Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram.

<https://hospital.uillinois.edu/patients-and-visitors/international-medicine-unpub/volunteer-services>

***“Nothing liberates our greatness like the desire to help,
the desire to serve”***

-Marianne Williamson

Health Related Volunteer Opportunities in Champaign Area

Champaign County Humane Society

For those pursuing veterinary studies, or those who love animals this opportunity would be a great fit. After attending an orientation session and spending one shift with a staff member, volunteers are free to come and go at their own discretion. They can spend their time assisting with feeding the pets, lead as adoption counselors, and also socializing the animals.

http://www.cuhumane.org/Portals/0/PDF/volunteer%20Brochure%20updated_03_2016.pdf?ver=2016-05-20-104025-530

Champaign Public Health Department

This position is made available through a sponsorship with the Champaign County Medical Reserve Corps, which consists of medical and non-medical volunteers. Through this position, volunteers meet once a quarter for approximately 2 hours to discuss methods of emergency preparedness.

<https://www.illinoishelps.net/>

Clark and Lindsey

This organization is dedicated to providing services to older residents through a multitude of programs. Volunteers can designate their time by partaking in any one of the many activities they provide such as leading a game, leading fitness activities, social and party planning, cooking and baking with residents and many more. There are many ways volunteers can devote their time that would brighten the elders that reside at Clark and Lindsey! Interested applicants can send a message to the email below.

retire@clark-lindsey.com

Carle Foundation Hospital

Carle Hospital has one of the largest volunteer programs within the area with about 500 students. Volunteers help service patients in various ways as discussed with volunteer coordinators. Applicants must be at least 14 years old, provide immunization records and must apply by August 29 for the fall term, November 15th for the spring term, and April 15th for the summer term.

<https://www.volgistics.com/ex/portal.dll/ap?ap=1942650195>

University of Illinois at Urbana Champaign Medical Brigade May 2021 - Honduras

This upcoming event is taking place in Honduras from August 29, 2021 to September 4, 2021 and allows volunteers the chance to travel to different locations every year in order to shadow doctors, assess vitals, assist in pharmaceutical operations under the guidance of pharmacists, and much more. Through this unique experience, volunteers can create partnerships and relationships with the communities they aid to provide follow up care and ensure long lasting health services. There is a cost of \$2,250 but donations to meet this goal are acceptable and encouraged!

For more information, interested applicants can sign up at the link below:

<https://fundraise.globalbrigades.org/empowered/chapter/university-of-illinois-at-urbana-champaign-medical-brigades-chapter111/brigade/university-of-illinois-urbana-champaign-medical-brigade-may-2021-honduras>

Join the IPHA!

Purchasing an IPHA membership account is the best way to stay up-to-date with the latest news and updates involving Illinois public health and provides many tools to help you network with other Illinois public health professionals. Here is the link with more information: <https://www.ipha.com>. Click on the membership tab for information on how to join!

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